

“The Effects of Reward in Shaping Students Behavior” A Case Study in District Loralai, Balochistan, Pakistan

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: May 01, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: December 02, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords : Effects, Reward, Shaping, Students, Behavior</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5750851</p>	<p><i>This study examined the effects of rewards in shaping students' behavior. This qualitative study intended to probe the kinds of rewards given to students at school level. The current research aimed at the frequency and context of rewards specified for shaping students behavior and performance. The subjects of the study were 35 people containing of 30 students and 05 teachers from secondary classes of Balochistan Residential College (BRC). Thus, to obtain the required data, observation sheet and interview protocol were used, therefore, the raw data was recorded and narrated. For the analysis of qualitative data, codes, concepts, categories and themes were formed. Themes emerged from the analysis of structured interviews of teachers and students; the perception of teachers and students about tangible and intangible rewards in shaping the behavior of students. Miles & Huberman model was also used for the data reduction, data display and conclusion. The findings of the study were both intangible and tangible rewards given by the teachers. The teachers' perception of rewards was positive influence in the behavior of the students.</i></p>

Introduction

The teachers, educationists and other academicians have been working to secure the desired behavior of the students. For the obtaining of this purpose, various techniques and strategies are being adopted. Sometimes they are promised incentives and other rewards to mold their behavior towards positive and constructive directions. Saraswati, Ratminingsih&Utami (2020) explained that rewarding is indeed one of the most important factors which influence students' learning outcomes and development of their behaviors. They revealed about the teacher's as well as students' perception about rewards giving on the basis of outstanding performance.

Lee, Sturmey& Fields (2007) concluded that the success and implementation of rewarding the desired behavior can be a complex one subjecting on quantity of variables like the size and cost of the reward, possibilities in the environment, schedule of reward, and other environmental and gender factors. A number of researchers analyzed the study on different reinforcement conditions, in fact they have pointed out the real-world difficulties and other complications of using reinforcement in everyday settings. According to them, reinforcement needs the time and attention of the assessor who observe and administer rather than the prize or cost of the reward. These researchers revealed that students from various backgrounds have diverse inclinations on rewards which may work in one condition and does not work in another (Rehu, Lusk, & Wolff, 2005).

Ryan, Orton &Pimm (1968) concluded that several basic problems in motivation encompass the choices of reward themselves, generally collected as tangibles versus intangibles or recognition. For example, giving lower quantity of prizes or rewards may really be associated with advanced and higher performance than offering a large quantity of rewards. Deci (1972) described that the act of learning and completion is basically motivated and thus, tangible rewards are potentially damaging. Likewise, Pierce, Cameron, &Banko (2003) stated the sequencing of the rewards which have greater effect on motivation, for instance when reward is based on difficult criteria of performance, the motivation level improves.

Ormord (2004) revealed the facts that why reinforcement or rewards would not work in often occasions, its major reason is that the reinforcers are not reinforcing. Therefore, an important factor of positive reinforcement can be the use of rewards because reinforcements vary from student to student, thus the teachers should be well aware about reinforcement which students value and use them. Moreover, the reinforecer should be important to the children, otherwise the reinforcement will not work (Gargus, 2004).

Reed (2001) and Yukl, Latham, &Pursell (1976) revealed that the relation of scheduling and the frequency of rewards is too greater to motivation and results. Skinner (1938) argued that rewards may be offered in a continuous way on a pre-determined plan or on a variable schedule. The frequency and regularity with which rewards are offered was found in a number of researches to affect the chance or probability that wanted behavior would be repeated (Yukl, Wexley, and Seymour, 1972).

Otero (2015) stated that timely offered rewards to students are related to improved study skills, essential behavior and academic productivity. In this context, it is concluded that in similar way students will be motivated through the reinforcement of teachers to sustain their positive behavior. Downing, & Bennett (2005) analyzed that positive and constructive reinforcement strategy is more effective than punishing or demanding strategy for increasing to shape positive behavior in the school environment.

Alacapinar (2016) described that rewards and teacher's own behavior can intentionally affect the pupils' cognitive, psychomotor, affective and intuitional behavior. Bennett (2012) stated that positive reinforcement is very essential when there is misconduct in the classroom. Condry (1977) revealed that for many years even before the formation of Skinner's theory of operant conditioning, students were rewarded for good and positive behavior.

Covington & Mueller (2001) suggested that rewards such as grades also play a vital role in the behavior, progress and competence of students because grades are very powerful through a teacher can judge a student's overall success and failure in classroom. In addition, most individuals are agreed that grades can be positive reinforcers which increase the probability of progressive and positive behavior occur in the future. For instance, if a learner received an "A" on an assignment, he or she would certainly be more likely to prepare or study for the next assignment (Reeve, 2001). Conversely, many endeavors have been made to teach without grades; consequently, the students were less interested to study without rewarding grades (Mandrell, 1997). Moreover, in another study has determined that giving grades not only improvise students' motivation, but lay down significant effects on their behavior (Bressettee, 2002).

Vincent (1997) stated that an actual way to control behaviors of enslaved youth an educational situation, positive reinforcement programs would be initiated. He found in his study that for fostering behavior change, rewards and incentives are rigorous factors offered in educational setting. Similarly, Cameron & Pierce (1994) investigated that both kind of intangible such as praise, feedback etc. and tangible like certificate and bookmarks etc. rewards can positively influence in shaping students' behavior. However, other researchers ((Brennan & Glover, 1980; Cameron & Pierce, 1994; McLoyd, 1979) have explained that under certain situations, extrinsic rewards can significantly enhance motivation, may be resulted in demonstrating positive behavior. Causes that seem to result in improved core motivation are interest in the educational activity (McLoyd, 1979).

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the current study is to reveal the pertinent role of tangible and intangible rewards in shaping students' behavior in school setting. This study also aimed at, the perception of teachers and students about the significance of rewards in teaching learning process.

Research Questions

What effects do tangible rewards have in Shaping Students' Behavior?

What effects do intangible rewards have in Shaping Students' Behavior?

Methodology

This case study belongs to phenomenological research for the reason that it explores different responses to, or perceptions of, a specific phenomenon (Fraenkel&Wallen, 2009). The current study depicts the quality of phenomenon generally the application of rewards in Balochistan Residential College (BRC), District Loralai. Moreover, to know the perception of the teachers and students about providing rewards for shaping the behavior of students. The subjects of this study were the higher secondary students and teachers of BRC which were 30 students and 05 teachers. Before visiting the school, a consent was requested which was approved from the principal. Thus, to obtain the required data, observation sheet and interview protocol were used, therefore the raw data was recorded and narrated. For the analysis of qualitative data, codes, concepts, categories and themes were formed. Themes emerged from the analysis of structured interviews of teachers and students regarding their perception of tangible and intangible rewards in shaping the behavior of students. Miles & Huberman model was also employed for the data reduction, data display and conclusion.

Miles & Huberman (1994) concluded that qualitative data analysis contains of three simultaneous flows of activity which are data reduction, data display and conclusion.

Result and Discussion

Types of Reward Used in Balochistan Residential College (BRC)

Table No. 01 Composition of kinds of rewards and data analysis

No	Types of Rewards	Examples
1	Intangible	08
2	Tangible	03

Table No. 01 shows that two types are rewards namely: tangible and intangible are offered to the children. Among these rewards 08 intangible and 03 tangible are given to the students of BRC. In tangible rewards consist of excellent, outstanding, wonderful, fantastic great efforts, well done, and amazing. Similarly, tangible rewards are rarely given whenever the students perform well especially in terminal examination. During interviews their class-teacher told the researcher that tangible rewards are given to the top position holders. Therefore, it was found that 03 pencil boxes, 05 merit certificates and 01 story book as tangible rewards were given.

Table No. 02 Composition of kinds, frequency of rewards and data analysis

No	Types of Rewards	Frequency	Percentage %
01	Excellent	10	11.23
02	Outstanding	09	10.11
03	Wonderful	13	14.60
04	Fantastic	07	7.87
05	Great Efforts	11	12.36
06	Well Done	14	15.73
07	Amazing	05	5.61
08	Very Good	12	13.49
09	Pencil Box	03	3.38
10	Merit Certificate	04	4.50
11	Book	01	1.12
	Total	89	100.00

Table No. 02 shows justification that most often rewards were given to the learners respectively are: well done, wonderful, very good, great efforts, excellent, outstanding, fantastic, and amazing. Indeed the above table depicts that intangible reward are frequently given than tangible reward. During interview with teachers, it is supported that intangible or verbal rewards are easy and simple to be given. It can also be observed in the table 02 that the frequency of intangible rewards which mostly displays the learners' responses is right. Secondly, if the above frequency is examined, it shows that learners are actively participating in their classes. Casern (2006) found that frequent feedback from the tests is more effective to improvise the students' performance. The idea established on the observation that was followed by interview process, it may be acceptable that rewards are given in the context of right answer and close to the correct answer with some tolerated mistakes.

Chen & Wu (2010) stated that rewards may serve reinforcement that enhances the probability for the desired behavior. Positive behavior indicates active participation of the learners during instruction. A number of studies show that praise or appreciation is a very effective tool for shaping students behavior in the desired direction.

The above table shows that tangible rewards are rarely given, during interview the teachers had the opinions that tangible rewards are expensive to be purchased, but they admitted that it increases the spirit of competition among the students. Theodoteu (2014) discovered that rewards can easily reinforce and at the same time anticipate the students' inclination to learn because reward is stimulation towards learning activities. The learners happily join the learning activities as fun and they may feel proud of themselves when they get appreciation or praise in the shape of reward.

Themes emerged from the interview transcripts of teachers

Theme1. The Effects of Intangible Rewards on Shaping Students' Behavior

Majority of the teachers have strong perception that reward increases the interest level of students, one of the teachers said, "I always appreciate the students whenever they show me their complete note books" (T1). Therefore, all the teachers were agreed that they (students) show positive behavior towards any assignment or homework. As one senior teacher shared his experiences, "This is a human nature to be pleased on getting appreciation or complement, even a child or a 60 years old person loves to be praised or rewarded" (T3). Similarly, all the teachers had positive responses about perception of rewards which augment the interest level of students.

When the investigator asked an open-ended question to know their opinion about the intangible rewards in school system, for example excellent, very nice, wonderful, good job, fantastic, great, perfect, well done, nice try, amazing, awesome etc. Mostly teachers said that intangible rewards cost nothing but students feel great honor and respect for themselves. They had the opinion that positive remarks increase their learning outcomes. One interviewee expressed that he had never given the remark "Poor" to any of his students because negative remarks discourage a student and consequently, feels inferior in the entire class (T1).

The researcher wanted to know their opinions that how rewards effect on the behavior of the students. Majority of the teachers had the opinion that rewards boost up their morale in academics achievements as well as they (students) behave nicely. They added that the rewards should be given immediately after doing the task.

Khansir&Dehkordi (2017) stated that feedback as an appreciation is also a kind of reward, when the students are appreciated their motivation level increases and behave positively. Howard & Jay (2016) suggested that variety of using verbal rewards is significant to be done. Therefore, rewards for the learners should be designed and modified as creative or inventive as possible. Among these teachers one of them said, “Too many verbal rewards have negative effect on students’ behavior because such frequent and habitual rewards lose their effect and worth. The students are taking such rewards for granted” (T2). Another teacher said, “I often associate the reward with right answer, showing positive repeated behavior in the classroom and even I share the same idea with parents in parent-teacher meeting. I suggest the parents to condition gifts or other rewards with high academic achievement when they want to give their children” (T5).

Theme2. The Effects of Tangible Rewards on Shaping Students’ Behavior

Besides intangible rewards, tangible rewards are also given in schools by the teachers. The investigator was interested to reveal the teachers opinion about the tangible rewards in school system. Majority of the teachers had the opinion that tangible rewards are rarely given to the students. They stated that as compared to verbal rewards, concrete or tangible rewards have more effects on the students. One of the interviewees said, “Tangible rewards are more vivid which can be kept forever and secondly parents also appreciate such rewards. He stated that the effective consequences of rewards are to decrease students’ negative behavior and increase positive behavior” (T5). Aypay (2018) analyzed that feedback to the students in the form of reward is more effective as external intervention to behavior that may be used for various purposes.

The researcher asked to know the teachers’ perception about tangible rewards whether these rewards create the spirit of competition among the students. Mostly teachers stated that everyone likes receiving positive rewards because effective positive rewards reinforce the things the student is doing well and motivate them to keep doing it. One of the teachers said, “If you want to lessen the negative consequences of rewards then positive reward needs to be immediate which means a reward should be given as soon as possible after the positive behavior. This is my personal experiences which help the students connect the reward with their positive behavior” (T4). They had the opinion that tangible rewards are costly to be purchased, thus such kind of rewards should be provided from the school administration. Another teacher expressed, “I always prefer to give important reward to the students which means a reward that can be meaningful to the students whether tangible or intangible” (T3). They suggested that rewards should be consistent which means a reward will be given every time the behavior happens, thus to be consistent have a list of rewards beforehand. Moreover, they stated that positive reward needs to be the right size and degree which means how big or small the reward is. The effective positive reward should match the degree of the positive behavior.

Themes emerged from the interview transcripts of students

Theme1. The Effects of Intangible Rewards on Shaping Students’ Behavior

Most of the students have solid insight that reward increases the interest level of students among them one of the students said, “I always share good remarks of the teachers with my parents, brother, sisters and friends and when I receive a poor remark on my classwork or homework, then I avoid share with my relatives and friends” (S2). They expressed their views that they love to receive rewards from their teachers for example; excellent, very nice, wonderful, superb, good job, fantastic, great, perfect, well done, nice try, amazing, awesome etc. One of the students shared his views, “I always try to keep my position high in my class because for the last two years I stood 3rd position in the class of 30 students” (S7).

The researcher required to know the students feelings that how rewards effect on their behavior in the classroom setting. A great number of them had the opinion that rewards encourage them and they pay more respect to those teachers who utter praising and appreciative words. It was revealed that one’s ideal or favorite teacher is one who every time appreciates the right answer and positive behavior of the students. One of the students said that his favorite teacher is Mr. ‘X’ who never scolded him but always advised him to improve his writing skill (S1). Therefore, rewards should always be purposeful. Guendouze&Abderrahim (2012) stated that reward can easily stimulate the learners to enhance their interest or motivation towards studies in effective way. For that purpose, reward ought to be given on every positive behavior as effective as possible. The teacher should give reward correctly because sometimes the teacher face sensitive learners who are actually deserve but with little misconception of the teacher they are deprived from the rewards.

Theme2. The Effects of Tangible Rewards on Shaping Students’ Behavior

In addition, tangible rewards are given mostly after successful promotion from one class to another. Similarly, the investigator fascinated to identify the students opinion about tangible rewards in school setting. Mostly students expressed their views that only the top three students who stood respectively; first, second and third in the examination receive tangible rewards. One of them said, “Since my school life, I have received three awards in shape of shields which I put them in my room and whenever our relatives or guests visit my room, those reward capture their attention and I feel cheerful” (S5).

Saraswati, Ratminingsih&Utami (2020) concluded that rewards enable the students to interact with teachers and others. When the students are assigned any task or assignment, they would be motivated to prepare the given work if there is any reward. Students will willingly answer the questions and feel happy when they are rewarded for the right answer. Burton et al., (2003) revealed that reward to everything which promotes a behavior continuously repeated in the future. Indeed, giving the rewards, the learners would be confident and desire to achieve again and again the rewards. Similarly, they would perform their best yet again in the future, so that to fulfill the required target to receive the reward.

Conclusion

The study determines the effects of rewards in shaping students' behavior in Balochistan Residential College (BRC) at District Loralai. On the basis of discussion and findings, it is concluded that teachers use both intangible and tangible rewards in BRC. The most frequent rewards given to the students were found verbal or intangible in order of: well-done, wonderful, very good, great efforts, excellent, outstanding, fantastic, and amazing etc. Secondly, rewards were given in two contexts, namely: right answer and close to the correct answer with some tolerated mistakes. In this way, the students remain enthusiastic for receiving the rewards. Moreover, the teachers have positive view about rewards. They believed that through rewards their achievement level and positive behavior will go on consistent. The teachers expressed their views that praise and appreciation can be an effective method to energize the learners. In addition, it can strengthen teacher-student connection. Few tangible rewards were awarded but they had the opinion that tangible rewards are given in the annual prize distribution ceremony, which include merit certificates, trophies, shields and stationery items. They admitted that these kinds of rewards motivate the students to excel in studies and positively behave inside and outside the classroom.

Recommendations

Rewards should always be in recognition, and for the encouragement of continued effort. These rewards must not be given for any solitary performance, or to that student whose family condition is favorable, and the one who is gifted having the highest IQ level, and always gets a remarkable place in any task or in the routine of behavior or conduct. Moreover, a diligent toiler, a careful learner who has been making a constant effort, deserve a reward more than the previous kind of student, who acquires the regular reward of his better home services and intelligence in other way.

Tangible rewards ought to be as limited as possible for the adult students, in case of junior students; it will be desirable to employ this incentive more frequently in order to help in the development of good habits and behaviors.

Rewards should be of low fundamental or intrinsic value. They are just marks of recognition and not valuable possessions to be coveted; otherwise they appeal to material considerations and supply low motives for behavior.

Consequently, younger the student and the lower the grade of his intelligence the more immediate the reward should be. Intimacy of sequence inaugurates the connection easily.

Finally, it is strongly recommended that the school administration needs to allocate some amount every year, for the purchasing of tangible rewards, so that the teacher rewards the students for an outstanding performance in both academically and behaviorally.

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